

AN ANALYTICAL OVERVIEW OF THE SAT PREPARATION IN VIETNAM

LAB University of Applied Sciences
Bachelor of Business Administration, International Business
2025
Phuong Nga Nguyen

Statement about using AI

The author of this thesis, Nga Nguyen, is responsible for the accuracy of the contents of the thesis, including content generated with AI. AI was used in this work during background research and later for language editing.

Background research made use of ChatGPT (An AI tool developed by OpenAi company).

The following prompts were entered on September 7, 2025: What is methodology in academic research and what types of data collection methods exist?

The author used the information from these prompts to identify relevant keywords (such as "quantitative" and "qualitative research") and to verify them with academic sources available online.

The following prompt was entered on October 8, 2025: What frameworks can be used to evaluate multiple companies or an entire industry at the same time?

The author reviewed the suggested frameworks and conducted additional research to identify academic materials supporting the thesis.

The following prompts were entered on October 25, 2025: What frameworks are commonly used to evaluate customer segments and customer behavior?

The author reviewed the suggested frameworks and conducted additional research to identify academic materials supporting the thesis.

The following prompts were entered on November 13, 2025: Besides PESTEL and SWOT, what additional models can be used to analyze and evaluate a specific subject such as the SAT?

The author used this information to design a structure for chapter 2: SAT market overview

The following prompts were entered on November 30, 2025: What is the purpose of a future research section, what is required in this part, and provide types of guiding questions help structure it in relation to original aims, achievements, and limitations?

The author used this information to understand what should be included in the conclusion chapter and then drafted the content independently based on the suggested guiding questions.

QuillBot (an AI-powered writing tool) was used for language checking to ensure linguistic correctness. The use was occasional throughout the thesis.

The authenticity of this thesis has been checked with the Turnitin similarity checking software.

		Abstract
Author(s)	Publication type	Completion year
Phuong Nga Nguyen	Thesis, UAS	2025
	Number of pages	
41		
Title of the thesis		
An Analytical Overview of the SAT Preparation in Vietnam		
Degree, Field of Study		
International Business		
Name, title and organization of the client		
Abstract		
<p>The thesis explores the SAT market in Vietnam through research on customers and SAT preparation centers. The thesis objective is to provide an overview of the SAT preparation market in Vietnam.</p> <p>The qualitative data includes customer behavior, psychology, and motivation, while quantitative data covers course pricing, duration, and structure. The thesis examines the history and evolution of the SAT. Customer analysis is conducted through market segmentation, including demographic, geographic, psychographic, and behavioral factors. This analysis reveals the differences among customer groups and how each segment influences purchasing decisions. About 10 SAT preparation centers in Vietnam were analyzed to gather information on course structure, prices, class sizes, and duration.</p> <p>The thesis aims to provide a detailed understanding of the needs, expectations, and motivations of customers. In the end, the thesis offers insights to help marketers understand how SAT courses are organized and identify target customers to develop suitable strategies.</p>		
Keywords		
SAT Launch, Online course, Price model, SAT Market, SAT's learners, SAT centers, Segmentation base, VALS Framework		

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1 Introduction

1.1 Research Background

In 1926, the Scholastic Assessment Test, also known as the SAT, was introduced by the College Board. This is an entrance exam that is widely used to evaluate the academic ability of high school students before they enter university, mainly used in the United States, Canada, Australia and several European countries. (IIG Viet Nam.)

In Vietnam, the demand for the SAT exam has been increasing recently for some of the following reasons. Since 2023, more universities have accepted SAT scores for both direct and general admission, which includes National Economics University (Hanoi), National Economics University, Foreign Trade University and the National Economics University (IIG Vietnam 2023). Another reason for taking the SAT is that more Vietnamese students plan to study abroad in the US and many of the universities there require SAT scores for admission. Therefore, numerous SAT preparation centers have been established, initially focusing mainly on offline teaching.

However, the COVID-19 pandemic created many challenges in organizing in-person classes. Thus, online classes became popular and offered a practical solution for modern education. In response, many companies have developed online SAT preparation courses, leading to a highly competitive market.

1.2 Objectives, Research Questions and Delimitations

Research objectives:

The objective of this thesis is to provide a comprehensive overview of the SAT preparation market in Vietnam. This thesis describes the current market structure, characteristics of SAT learners and the operations of existing SAT centers in the country.

Specifically, the thesis analyzes customer profiles, learning needs and their decision-making behaviors when they choose a place to take an SAT course. In addition, the thesis seeks to find out how SAT centers operate by investigating their course offerings, pricing strategies, brand positioning and marketing activities. The insights from this thesis could offer valuable guidance for individuals and organizations interested in launching a SAT center, as well as those who are building or developing their courses to better align with current market demands.

Research questions and sub-questions:

Main question: What is the current structure and landscape of the SAT preparation market in Vietnam?

Sub-questions:

RQ1: What are the main learner segments in Vietnam's SAT preparation market?

This sub-question helps explore the characteristics of SAT learners in Vietnam's preparation market. Understanding the learner segment helps form a clear picture of the overall market landscape.

RQ2: What types of SAT preparation providers operate in Vietnam?

This sub-question helps categorize the different types of SAT centers operating in Vietnam. The focus is on clarifying their operational model, scale, pricing and branding to create a more balanced picture from a supply-side perspective. The insights provide a foundation for answering the main research question.

Delimitations:

This thesis examines the SAT preparation market in Vietnam, including the characteristics of customers, types of providers, pricing, and branding in the market. However, it does not evaluate the impact of teaching methods to compare the learning outcomes between different providers.

1.3 Theoretical Framework

Market Segmentation

The thesis applies the market segmentation framework discussed by Kotler and Keller (2012) to investigate SAT customers in Vietnam. Market segmentation is the process of categorizing buyers into different groups based on their characteristics. Each group has specific needs and preferences, allowing businesses to create specific approaches that meet the requirements of their target customers.

The segmentation method is chosen because it provides a comprehensive view of the demand side of the SAT market. It allows companies to identify which customer groups align most closely with their capabilities and available resources. By understanding these different segments, businesses or organizations can decide which groups of customers they can serve the best and develop suitable strategies to satisfy these specific needs.

Based on Kotler and Keller's (2012) framework, there are four main categories: Demographic, Geographic, Psychographic, and Behavioral. Firstly, Demographic and Geographic Segmentation are used to answer the question, "Who are the learners?"

In order to answer the question, the geographic segmentation provides information on the customers' living place, the population density of the area and their surrounding community. Other demographic factors such as age, life cycle stage, gender, income level and educational background are also analyzed.

Psychographic and Behavioral Segmentation are applied to analyze learning behaviors, course selection criteria and pain points on the demand side. This analysis is based mostly on customers' lifestyles, resources loyalty status, occasions, knowledge level and their attitudes toward the SAT product. Both of these segmentation types help identify what motivates learners and how their resources influence their perception of SAT courses.

VALS Framework

Additionally, this thesis will utilize the VALS framework developed by SRI International. This model describes the motivations and resources of consumers. Consumer motivations are derived from three primary drivers: ideals, achievement, and self-expression. These motivations are manifested through an individual's resources. The more resources a person possesses, the greater their capacity to fulfill their motivations. Resources include health, education, income, age, energy, and intelligence. These factors vary among individuals and, when combined with motivation groups, create distinct consumer types. These consumer types include Innovators, Thinkers, Achievers, Experiencers, Believers, Strivers, Makers, and Survivors. This analysis will examine each consumer type and analyze their needs and desires regarding SAT preparation courses. This section supports the psychographic segmentation analysis.

1.4 Research Methodology and Data Collection

This thesis uses a mixed-method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative data to build a complete overview of Vietnam's SAT preparation market. All of the information in this thesis was collected through both primary and secondary data.

Qualitative data is collected to understand how SAT centers operate and place themselves in the marketplace. Specifically, it includes business profiles, operational models, course structures, brand positioning, targeted clients and their behaviors. The

sources include center websites, social media, course brochures and official reports on education trends and study abroad in Vietnam.

Quantitative data delivers measurable data that allows objective comparison across SAT centers. It covers tuition fees, number of course offerings, class sizes, course duration, discounted pricing options and product tiering (e.g., Beginning, Intermediate, Advanced). These data points allow us to compare centers in a systematic way.

On the other hand, secondary data sources include reports from reliable sources, including government education reports, industry publications, market research reports, marketing and pricing books, SAT center websites and their sale materials and other public communications sources.

Furthermore, beyond secondary data from websites and social media, course information was also collected through direct communication with sales consultants of numerous SAT providers. This includes information from Viet Accepted, American Study, Stella Education, Summit Education, DOL English, Phoenix Prep, QAS Academy, and ECE, gathered through Facebook Messenger, Zalo, and phone calls. These conversations provided information on course fees, class sizes, course duration, teaching formats, and course structures. This primary data, combined with secondary sources, was input into a database using Google Sheets. This includes SAT centers' general information, course offerings, prices, and duration. The details are provided in Appendix 1.

1.5 Thesis Structure

Figure 1 describes the structure of this thesis. The thesis focuses on the SAT market in Vietnam, specifically analyzing two main factors: the customer side and the provider side. Starting with the Introduction, which provides an overview of the SAT context, explains the reasons for choosing this topic, discusses the research methodology, and presents the theoretical framework used in this thesis.

Chapter 2 delves into greater detail about the SAT exam, discussing its history and development, as well as the global expansion of the SAT, including its specific presence in Vietnam. This chapter brings readers a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the SAT examination.

Chapter 3 analyzes the demand-side perspective utilizing a segmentation-based method to better understand the profile of students who demonstrate the need to study for the SAT in Vietnam. As a result, this provides key insights into learners' demographics, their

motivations, expectations, and learning approaches, as well as the obstacles and pain points they face.

Chapter 4 analyzes the SAT providers in the Vietnamese market. It provides information about existing SAT preparation centers and categorizes them into different types based on pricing, what courses they offer, how long they have been established, and other factors.

Chapter 5 summarizes and discusses the thesis's achievements and the existing limitations.

2 Market Overview: Vietnam's SAT Preparation Landscape

2.1 Overview of the SAT Exam

This section explores the history of the SAT, from its origins in early 20th-century America to its development over more than a century, including changes in name and test structure.

2.1.1 The SAT: History and Evolution

The SAT is a standardized test that has become widely used and recognized as one of the most common assessments among students. The primary purpose of this examination is to be utilized extensively to assess and evaluate the academic capabilities and aptitude of high school students before they make their transition into college-level education. (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168.)

However, it is notable that few people are aware of the historical origins of this examination, which trace back to the late 19th century. During this period, a substantial wave of immigration entered the United States, creating significant demographic shifts. Consequently, this phenomenon situation caused the number of high school students to increase dramatically and beyond what was initially anticipated. (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168.)

Moreover, this demographic situation coincided with the historical context that the United States had to participate in World War I, during which the military faced an urgent need for intelligent individuals who could serve as leaders and commanders. In contrast, those individuals with lower aptitudes and capabilities would be assigned to participate directly in battlefield operations rather than in leadership or strategic roles. (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168.)

It can be said that this was the perfect opportunity and the ideal moment for them to be able to create a special examination that had the capability to assess and evaluate the level of intelligence and mental capacity of over 2 million recruits. Furthermore, this was also the largest-scale examination that had ever existed in history at that point. (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168.)

This examination was subsequently evaluated and tested thoroughly over an extended period and the results demonstrated that it could accurately assess the capabilities of each individual. The validity and reliability of this test were further examined and verified by distinguished scholars such as Lewis Terman, Carl Brigham and E. L. Thorndike.

These scholars, who were recognized as erudite and credible researchers in the field of psychology and educational measurement, officially endorsed and validated the examination as a reliable assessment tool. (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168.)

Finally, by 1926, Carl Brigham, who had previously worked with the team to create the aforementioned military examination, developed a new version of this test that was specifically adapted for college students at Princeton University and Cooper Union, which was a technical college at that time. (Jacobsen 2024.)

In 1899, the College Entrance Examination Board was established by 12 prestigious universities in the United States, which nowadays is known by its shorter name, the College Board (Jacobsen 2024). The organization worked to adapt and modify existing examinations to better suit college admissions purposes. On June 23, 1926, the SAT was officially administered for the first time. Initially, this standardized examination was called the Scholastic Aptitude Test (Manhattan Review).

However, this particular nomenclature created problematic associations with other aptitude-based assessments, most notably the Intelligence Quotient (IQ) test. These associations evoked public memories of IQ testing practices that had risen to widespread prominence from the early 20th century onward (Lemann 2000, 24, according to Berger 2012, 167-168), subsequently causing significant issues regarding public perception. The president of the College Board believed that this naming convention created a widespread misconception among the public. Specifically, many people mistakenly assumed that high SAT scores were based on innate ability rather than preparation and therefore could not be improved through practice. For this reason, in 1990, the examination was renamed the Scholastic Assessment Test (Manhattan Review).

However, the evolution of the test's naming did not end at that point. During the spring season of 1997, the College Board made yet another significant announcement declaring that the acronym SAT would no longer serve as an abbreviation standing for Scholastic Assessment Test and that moving forward, they would instead regard and treat SAT as a distinct and independent brand name or trademark in its own right. (Manhattan Review.)

2.1.2 SAT Structure

After many significant changes to the test structure and alongside the development of the technological environment, the SAT Digital was introduced internationally in 2023 and later in the United States in 2024. This digital test helped optimize the logistical preparation work required when administering the SAT examination. Additionally, the scoring process

and the delivery of scores to test-takers became more accurate and faster (EDUSYNCH 2024).

Regarding the test structure, the SAT changed quite significantly in terms of duration and the nature of the modules. Specifically, the time to complete the examination has been reduced from 3 hours to only 2 hours and 14 minutes. The examination sections are organized into 2 main parts: Reading & Writing section and Math section. Each of these sections is subdivided into 2 modules and these modules possess adaptive functionality. (College Board a.)

Specifically, if a test-taker successfully completes Module 1 of the Reading and Writing section with satisfactory results, meaning that they answer nearly all questions correctly, then upon proceeding to Module 2, they will be switched to a harder version. Conversely, if the test-taker does not perform well on the first module, upon completion of that module, they will be transferred to module 2, which offers an easier version. Throughout this structure, each module lasts around 32 to 35 minutes (College Board a).

SAT			SAT-d		
Section	# of Questions	Time per Section	Section	# of Questions	Time per Section
Reading	52	65 mins	Reading and Writing 1	27	32 mins
Writing and Language	44	35 mins	Reading and Writing 2	27	32 mins
Math – No calculator	20	25 mins	- Break -		
Math - calculator	38	55 mins	Math 1	22	35 mins
Essay (optional)	1	50 mins	Math 2	22	35 mins
154		3:00 (3:50)	98		2 hours 14 mins

Figure 2: The differences between the old SAT test and the new Digital SAT (Source: Fairtest)

Figure 2 compares the differences between the old SAT and the digital SAT. It can be seen that the digital SAT has a clearer and simpler structure. The SAT is divided into two sections, each containing two modules. The duration of the old SAT was 3 hours, which has been reduced to 2.23 hours.

As a result, the introduction of the digital SAT not only reduced the total number of questions compared to previous paper-based versions but also enhanced the accuracy of scoring and assessment of test-takers' capabilities through this adaptive system.

2.2 The Global Expansion of the SAT

There are over 4,000 colleges and universities that use the SAT in their admissions process. These institutions include schools in the United States and 65 other countries (College Board b), notably such as Canada, the United Kingdom, Australia, New Zealand, several countries in the European region, and Asia.

Regarding the number of people taking the SAT examination, each year there are approximately 2 million test-takers participating in it worldwide. The United States accounts for the largest number, with approximately 1.87 million participants annually. This can be explained by the fact that most schools in the United States use the SAT examination as a key entrance criterion. (The Princeton Review 2025.)

Figure 3: Number of SAT Test-Takers by Country (adapted from The Princeton Review 2025)

Figure 3 shows the annual number of SAT test-takers from non-U.S. countries. It should be noted that the United States has been excluded from the figure 3 visualization because its number of SAT test-takers is significantly higher than that of other nations. This could make comparison with other countries difficult to visualize.

Following the United States, ranked 2nd and 3rd respectively are India and China, with the number of test-takers from India ranging from approximately 25,000 to 30,000 per year, and the number of test-takers from China ranging from approximately 20,000 to 25,000 for each year. This can be understood because the population of these 2 countries is exceptionally large, combined with their strong academic culture, which makes the number of people taking the SAT higher than other countries. For Indian students, they take the examination not primarily to apply to schools in the United States, but rather because most of the top universities in India require the SAT exam as part of their admissions criteria. (The Princeton Review 2025.)

Ranked 4th is South Korea, with the number of test-takers being approximately 8,000. In Korea, the SAT plays a significant role in university admissions, combined with the fact that Korean society places a high value on education, this creates a strong motivation for students to take the examination. People in Korea believe that the higher the degree they have, the more successful and professional they become, which may lead people to have better jobs and a higher living standard. (The Princeton Review 2025.)

2.2.1 The Rise of SAT Demand

Figure 4: Number of Vietnamese Students Taking the SAT from 2019 to 2023. (adapted from VNExpress 2024)

Figure 4 demonstrated the number of people taking the SAT examination in Vietnam has increased significantly since 2023. Specifically, in 2023, there were up to 3,510 people

participating in the SAT test, representing an increase of more than 74% compared to 2022 when this number was only 2,012 people (VnExpress 2024). This can be explained by the steady growth in the number of Vietnamese international students in recent years.

Figure 5 shows the number of Vietnamese students studying abroad in English-speaking countries such as the United States, Australia, the United Kingdom, and New Zealand from 2019 to 2023. Although the number of international students in the UK and New Zealand decreased, the figures for Australia and the US were generally significantly higher compared to the past two years (Thanh Nien 2024).

Figure 5: Vietnamese international students in English-speaking countries (adapted from Thanh Nien, 2024)

In addition, from the year 2024 to 2025, the number of Vietnamese students studying in the United States reached 25,600, and this is the highest number since the year 2000. According to the Open Doors report, which is an education report conducted by the non-profit organization IIE, Vietnam currently ranks among the top 5 countries in the world in terms of the number of students studying in the United States. Vietnam's position follows India, China, and South Korea, which occupy the top three spots, respectively. (VnExpress 2025.)

On the other hand, the majority of top universities and colleges in the US use the SAT as an important part of their admissions processes or consider it a strong point for applicants in their profiles. As a result, the number of people taking the SAT in Vietnam has increased significantly to meet this growing demand.

Another key reason behind the growing number of SAT participants is that universities in Vietnam have started to incorporate SAT scores into their admissions systems. This began in 2018, when Vietnam National University Hanoi became the first university in Vietnam to officially accept SAT scores for student admissions (Tuoi Tre 2018). This decision appeared to signal a significant shift in the admissions landscape for higher education. Specifically, in 2019, other prestigious universities such as Vietnam National University, Ho Chi Minh City, and Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education also began to adopt this admissions method.

By the year 2022, the number of universities accepting SAT scores for admissions had increased significantly to more than 15 universities across the country (Clever Academy 2022). As of 2025, this number has grown to nearly 30 universities in Vietnam that accept SAT scores for admissions (EATEST 2025). Notably, a significant proportion of these universities rank among the top educational institutions in Vietnam.

In Vietnam, there are currently 3 common forms of university admissions: direct admission, admission based on high school graduation examination scores, and combined admission. Among these, direct admission has a lower percentage compared to the other two forms. Typically, SAT scores are used in the combined admissions method. This means that universities will combine SAT scores with other factors such as international certificate scores, high school graduation examination scores, or the student's grade point average throughout their high school years.

2.2.2 SAT Testing Schedule, Costs, and Market Concentration

The SAT is administered 7 times per year, and this applies not only to Vietnam but across the entire world in all countries where the SAT is offered. Specifically, the examinations are scheduled during the months of March, May, June, August, October, November, and December. Particularly for the 2025-2026 academic year, there is an additional test date in September, bringing the total number of administrations up to 8 times per year (Zhang).

The standard cost of taking the SAT is 68 US dollars (USD), but this fee only applies to students taking the exam at testing centers located within the United States. For examinations conducted outside of the US, such as in Vietnam, test-takers are required to pay an additional fee of 43 dollars extra, which is the mandatory international testing fee. This extra charge brings the total cost up to 111 US dollars, equivalent to approximately 2,888,000 VND for students in Vietnam (depending on the exchange rate at the time of registration). (INEC.)

SAT preparation is mainly popular in major cities such as Ho Chi Minh City, Hanoi, and Da Nang as these are areas with large populations, high levels of economic development, better educational infrastructure, and more study abroad opportunities compared to other regions.

3 SAT Customer Analysis: Market Segmentation

3.1 Demographic and Geographic Segmentation

In this section, demographic and geographic segmentation will be used to build the profile of SAT course consumers in Vietnam. Geographic segmentation is one of the longest-used methods in marketing, helping businesses understand the differences in needs and consumer behavior across different geographic areas. On the other hand, demographic segmentation is also favored by many marketers because this method is easier to measure and has a direct connection to customers' needs and desires (Kotler & Keller 2012, 216).

3.1.1 Geographic Segmentation

In Vietnam, the SAT is more popular in large and developed cities, such as Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi. There are no official statistics on the number of English language centers or SAT preparation facilities across the country. However, the distribution of population, infrastructure, and economic development across different cities demonstrates this.

Specifically, in Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi City, the populations are 14 million and 8.8 million people, respectively, which is 2-3 times higher than smaller cities with populations ranging from 500,000 to nearly 4 million people (BankerVN 2025). The population density of these cities is also significantly high. Ho Chi Minh City has the highest density at 4,554.6 people per square kilometer, followed by Hanoi City with 2,594.7 people per square kilometer (General Statistics Office 2024).

Additionally, Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi are two of the largest economic centers in Vietnam, with GRDP (Gross Regional Domestic Product) of 63.65 billion USD and 51.39 billion USD respectively. The gap in economic scale between these cities and the remaining provinces is substantial. For example, the third-ranked city, Binh Duong, only reached 19.28 billion USD in the same period (Thu Vien Phap Luat 2024).

With high population density and strong economic development, these two cities have become driving forces for the development of Vietnam's education sector. Specifically, these places have substantial investment in infrastructure and physical facilities for developing education in general and supplementary courses like SAT courses in particular. Additionally, as the economy develops, the income of residents in these cities is also higher, giving them the financial capacity to invest in their children's education (Tran 2024). Moreover, families with better economic conditions tend to send their children to study abroad more than families in smaller cities. This leads to an increase in demand for

international certifications such as IELTS, SAT, and ACT exams. As a result, many SAT centers in Ho Chi Minh City and Hanoi City have emerged to meet this growing demand.

3.1.2 Demographic Segmentation

Age and Family Life Circle

As mentioned earlier, the SAT is a standardized test that evaluates students' abilities before entering university. Therefore, students usually begin to prepare for the SAT in high school, some even starting sooner, at the end of secondary school. The usual time needed to achieve the desired score depends on students' abilities. Students with a strong foundation in English and logical reasoning usually take 3 to 6 months of preparation, while other students with weaker foundations could take 6 months to 1.5 years or even more. As a result, many parents encourage their children to start SAT preparation early to have a clear understanding of their capabilities and get ready for the test (Tuoi Tre 2024a).

Additionally, students who prepare for the SAT early have more time to participate in extracurricular activities, prepare their university applications, study for their high school graduation exams, and prepare for entrance exams required by some universities. It can be seen that Vietnamese students who need to prepare for and take the SAT typically range from grades 9 to 12, equivalent to ages 14-18. This range can be extended to the ages of 14-20 to account for certain cases, such as students who decide to take a gap year after high school graduation to prepare for the SAT. They may use this time to prepare for the SAT in order to study abroad, apply for scholarships, and submit applications to Vietnamese universities if they are unable to prepare for it during their final year of high school. Therefore, this age range can fluctuate from 14 to 20 years old. This demographic belongs to Generation Z and early Generation Alpha, with Gen Z including those born from 1997 to 2009 and Gen Alpha including those born from 2010 to 2024 (Afamily 2021).

However, it is necessary to understand another demographic group from a different age range. This group is not the direct consumer of the product but has a significant influence on the purchase decision of SAT courses: the parents. According to pricing research discussed in detail in Chapter 4.3, a typical SAT course ranges from 9 to 20 million VND, which is equivalent to approximately \$360 to \$800 USD. To afford such a high price, parents usually make the decision instead of students.

Based on Kotler and Keller's (2012) family life cycle model, the target customers for SAT courses can be segmented into several groups: students from 14-20 or older who are the direct users, single parents with children aged 14-20 and above, married couples with

children aged 14-20 and above, and other family structures, including divorced parents or guardians with children aged 14-20 and above.

Gender

There are several studies indicating a difference in scores between males and females. In 2023, the average SAT score for males was about 9 points higher than for females, with males scoring 1032 and females scoring 1023 out of a total of 1600 points (Smith & Reeves 2025). In addition, more male students achieve higher scores than female students, and their average math scores are also higher.

Figure 6 illustrates SAT math scores from 2000 to 2018. 2016 saw a notable fluctuation, with scores significantly increasing. This can be explained by a change in the College Board's scoring system, from a maximum of 2400 points to 1600 points. Specifically, the old SAT had three sections, each worth 800 points, with Math being one of them and accounting for around 33% of the total score. In 2016, the new SAT structure was implemented with two main sections, and Math accounts for 50% of the total score. Overall, SAT scores for males and females have consistently maintained a gap over the years.

Figure 6: The difference between male and female SAT Math scores from 2000 to 2018 (Source: Erde & Barone, 2020)

Many people explain this by suggesting that male students achieve higher mathematics results in secondary and high school than female students. However, their reasoning does

not reflect the truth. In reality, female students tend to perform better and excel more than male students in mathematics at school (Perry 2016). Furthermore, female students' scores in AP (Advanced Placement) and Honors Math also surpass those of male students (Erde & Barone 2020).

There are several hypotheses about this existing gap. One of those suggests that the SAT is different from the typical math exercises taught in school curricula. Therefore, female students performing better in math and science at school does not necessarily translate to better scores compared to male students. Another hypothesis suggests that male students have better spatial visualization ability, which is the ability to imagine and process three-dimensional geometric forms. As a result, male students tend to achieve higher SAT Math scores. (Erde & Barone 2020.)

The discussion above shows the difference between males and females in overall scores and math scores specifically on the SAT. However, no research has shown gender differences regarding demands or needs in taking the SAT certification. Since this certification serves educational purposes, both male and female students pursue the same educational benefits that the SAT provides. Therefore, this section will not involve analyzing the demand and desire for SAT courses based on gender.

Education

The SAT exam plays a certain role in the college application portfolio of American students, but in Vietnam, the SAT is not widely adopted and remains optional for university admission. The decision to take the SAT exam depends on individual needs. Students typically choose to prepare for the SAT to study abroad, apply for better scholarships, or compete with other candidates for admission to top-tier universities within Vietnam. Therefore, SAT participation among students in this age group is not universal but rather concentrated among those with distinct educational backgrounds.

Learners typically aim to study abroad, secure scholarships, or make their portfolios stand out when applying to top universities in Vietnam. Secondly, in Vietnam, English is a second language for most students, while the SAT requires strong command of grammar and extensive vocabulary (ECE 2024a). Therefore, students require a sturdy English foundation to take the exam. Students from international schools, bilingual schools, or schools with enhanced English programs tend to have more advantages in accessing the SAT. This is because these educational environments naturally equip students with a strong English foundation.

Students' academic performance influences their educational aspirations (Allen 2024). Students with strong academic results have a higher tendency to seek greater achievements compared to students with weaker performance. Likewise, while the SAT is an optional examination in Vietnam and requires significant investment beyond the standard curriculum, this exam attracts more students with strong academic capabilities to pursue additional qualifications. In contrast, students with weaker academic outcomes typically spend most of their time and energy on meeting basic graduation requirements rather than pursuing optional standardized tests.

Based on these factors, the market can be segmented into different groups, which are students from public schools and private schools, including specialized schools and gifted schools. Other groups include students from international schools and bilingual schools. These schools typically have more students with study abroad goals and better English foundations compared to regular public schools.

The second perspective analyzes parents, who are the primary payers for SAT courses and exams. A study by Allen (2024) shows that parental education has an effect on their children's academic aspirations. Specifically, students with more educated parents tend to set higher academic goals than those from less educated families.

Another study examines the causal relationship between parents' and children's education. The study indicates that mothers with higher educational levels are more likely to create an environment that encourages their children to study (Lee et al. 2024, 28). These findings show that parents with higher educational levels are more likely to support and facilitate their children in pursuing additional courses, skills, and qualifications in general, and the SAT in particular.

Income And Social Class

Income is a key factor in market segmentation because it directly affects purchasing power and product affordability. However, income is not the determining factor in identifying potential customers for a product. For example, products designed to target upper-class customers may be favored by middle-class customer groups in reality. (Kotler & Keller 2012, 216.)

Income segmentation is a long-standing practice in such categories as automobiles, clothing, cosmetics, financial services, and travel. However, income does not always predict the best customers for a given product or service. (Kotler & Keller 2012, 216.)

According to the National Statistics Office (2025), the average income of Vietnamese people is 8.4 million VND per month. There is a significant income difference between urban and rural areas, with urban areas having an average salary of 10.1 million VND, which is 2.9 million VND higher than rural areas in the same period. This is because urban areas offer more job opportunities and have a higher cost of living compared to rural areas. In contrast, rural areas have fewer job opportunities but an affordable cost of living (Yu 2025).

On the other hand, SAT courses range from 9 to 20 million VND. It can be seen that the average monthly income of Vietnamese people is approximately equal to or lower than the cost of a typical SAT course. Moreover, this excludes other living expenses such as housing, food, and transportation, which must be deducted from the income before considering paying for an extra course. As a result, not all income groups can afford these courses. Therefore, the income levels of Vietnamese people can be divided into the following categories: 5-10 million VND per month, 10-20 million, 20-30 million, 30-40 million, 40-50 million, and 50 million or more.

Based on Kotler and Keller's segmentation approach, these income groups can be classified into the following segments, including Upper Lowers, Working Class, Middle Class, Upper Middles, Lower Uppers, and Upper Uppers.

3.2 Psychographic Segmentation: Motivations and Personal Resources

Following the analysis of demographic factors such as age, education, and income, it is necessary to incorporate psychographic segmentation. This approach provides a deeper understanding of potential customer behavior. This is one of the crucial segments to differentiate between customer types because people with similar demographic characteristics can display many different psychological profiles (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226). For instance, two families living in the same city with equal income may have different perspectives on education. One side is attracted to premium courses to demonstrate success, while the other focuses on the value and results that the courses provide.

3.2.1 VALS Framework Overview

In this section, I will use the VALS framework to analyze the psychographic segmentation. VALS stands for Values and Lifestyles, developed by Arnold Mitchell at SRI International in 1978 (Kahle et al. 1986, 405).

In the VALS model, customers are motivated by three main groups: Ideals, Achievement, and Self-expression. Each group represents a specific life value that people tend to pursue. For those driven by Ideals, customers' purchasing decisions are guided by their personal knowledge and internal principles, meaning that their consumption behavior is shaped by what they believe is right according to their own viewpoints. The Achievement group consumes products, motivated by the belief that possessing certain items will signal status and success, thereby gaining social recognition. The last group is motivated by Self-expression, including people who consume products to express their individuality and freedom. They tend to seek novelty or adventurous experiences. (Kotler & Keller 2012, 22.)

To evaluate how capable individuals are in pursuing these motivations, the model relies on personal resources. These resources include financial capability, age, energy, health, education, and similar attributes. The higher the level of resources, the more easily a person can fulfill and express their motivations. (Edublogs.)

To further clarify and categorize consumers, Mitchell divides them into eight major consumer groups based on the combination of their primary motivations and their level of resources. Figure 7 illustrates the original VALS framework. The model is structured along two axes: the horizontal axis represents the three primary motivations, while the vertical axis shows how consumer groups are distributed according to high or low levels of resources. (Nghia 2015.)

Figure 7: The VALS Framework (Source: Kotler & Keller, 2012, 226)

3.2.2 Ideals-Motivated Consumers: Thinkers and Believers

The Ideals group consists of people who are motivated by ideals and hold strong beliefs (Kim 2022). This group is divided into two types based on resource levels: Thinkers and Believers.

Thinkers

Thinkers have high resources and are motivated by their ideals and beliefs. They are typically well-educated people who value order and responsibility (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226). Their purchasing decisions are based on careful evaluation using their knowledge and experience.

Thinkers belong to the high-resource group, believe in their capabilities and knowledge, and are driven by ideals. This group is mostly highly educated individuals who value order and responsibility (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226). They make purchasing decisions for products or services based on their knowledge and experience. Thinkers seek SAT

courses because they genuinely need them, after careful thought and consideration, rather than following trends or social pressure.

Based on the characteristics of Thinkers, SAT centers with outstanding curriculum, reasonable study schedules, and highly qualified SAT teachers will attract them. It is important to have a consultation approach that is straightforward, comprehensive, and honest for this group. At the end, a thinker's decision to pay for a SAT course depends on their feelings about the necessity and worth of the money and time they invest.

Believers

Similarly, Believers are also motivated by strong beliefs. However, their beliefs are not centered on themselves but on external sources (Bhasin 2025). These sources can be religion, tradition, family, or community (Nghia 2015). Believers prioritize familiar brands and products for consumption and tend to be conservative to protect their beliefs.

From these characteristics, it can be seen that Believers are more likely to select reputable and well-established SAT centers. They prefer traditional teaching methods, physical classrooms, and printed materials over online learning platforms. When approaching this segment, SAT centers should emphasize trust, stability, and low risk.

3.2.3 Achievement-Motivated Consumers: Achievers and Strivers

This group prioritizes their achievements and the recognition they receive from others. Depending on the customers' available resources, this group divides into two types: Achievers and Strivers

Achievers

This is a high-resource group. Achievers focus on their family and career (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226). They consume premium and luxury products as a way to demonstrate their success in life.

To attract Achievers, SAT centers must position their products as premium or VIP courses with high quality. Marketing strategies designed for this group should highlight achievements that learners could gain after completing the course. For example, centers can use testimonials from former students with high SAT scores who are currently studying at top-tier universities. This approach appeals to Achievers' desire for recognition and success.

Strivers

Strivers also pursue achievement similarly to Achievers, but due to limited resources, they are called the "strivers" group. Strivers tend to purchase premium and trendy products but typically wait until these products are on sale (Nghia 2015).

To attract this group, the course needs to be positioned as high-quality, stylish, and trendy. Since Strivers enjoy the feeling of achievement, course design should be divided into small, easily achievable lessons with a clear reward system. For instance, online learning applications with attractive interfaces can integrate congratulatory notifications, badges, and points after each completed lesson. This aims to create continuous learning motivation for learners.

3.2.4 Self-Expression-Motivated Consumers: Experiencers and Makers

This group seeks products as a way to express and reveal their personal identity, which is divided into two types: Experiencers and Makers.

Experiencers

Experiencers have high resources and are characterized by youthful energy and enthusiasm. They enjoy novelty and adventure and place minimal concern for others' opinions. They spend the majority of their income on products and services that promote self-expression, such as fashion, entertainment, and social activities (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226).

To attract Experiencers, SAT courses must be flexible and have engaging content. Courses that lack dynamism or are excessively lengthy will cause learners to lose interest and motivation. Additionally, SAT centers should consider integrating social events, meetups, and networking sessions with like-minded individuals into their course structure.

Makers

Makers also enjoy self-expression, but their limited resources lead them to take a different approach. Makers express themselves through hands-on activities such as creating, building, repairing, or maintaining physical products (Kotler & Keller 2012, 227). They enjoy activities such as painting, gardening, woodworking, renovating homes, or fixing vehicles (Nghia 2015).

Makers purchase products and services relying on practical utility and functionality instead of trends or any social influence. When considering a course, they carefully consider the necessity for their life and ensure the cost fits their budget.

3.2.5 Resource Extremes: Innovators and Survivors

Innovators and Survivors represent two opposite ends of the VALS framework. Innovators possess the most abundant resources, while Survivors have the most limited resources.

Innovators

Innovators are successful individuals positioned at the top of the VALS resource ranking. Unlike other segments, Innovators' decisions are not dominated by a single motivation. Rather than being constrained by motivations, Innovators actively control and balance all three primary motivations, including ideals, achievement, and self-expression. They possess characteristics such as confidence, intelligence, a strong appreciation for innovation, and natural leadership abilities (Kotler & Keller 2012, 226).

To successfully reach this group, SAT centers should avoid traditional mass marketing strategies and instead focus on niche markets. Specifically, one-on-one teaching packages or VIP/platinum courses would suit them well. Additionally, centers must regularly organize expert seminars with leading education specialists. This provides a premium and unique experience for Innovators' "sophisticated" tastes (Edublogs).

Survivors

Survivors belong to the lowest-resource segment, formed by older age and passive behavior. Their primary concerns focus on fulfilling basic daily needs and maintaining stability rather than pursuing goals beyond basic needs (Bhasin 2025). As a result, this group is typically not the primary target for the SAT market. However, if centers choose to attract this segment, they must consider offering courses with affordable prices, simple content, straightforward access, and low risk.

3.3 Behavioral Segmentation: Decision Roles in Course Purchase

In the process of purchasing a certain product, there can be more than one person influencing the purchase decision-making process. Understanding who influences these decisions helps businesses develop more effective sales strategies, with each strategy tailored to a specific group. Those who have an impact on the decision to purchase SAT courses are divided into the following groups, including Initiator, User, Influencer, Decider, and Buyer (Kotler & Keller 2012, 227). The sections below will analyze the identity of these stakeholders and provide marketers with insights on how to capitalize on this information to optimize sales effectiveness.

3.3.1 Initiator

Initiators are those behind creating the idea of purchasing. They recognize the problem and bring it up to be solved (College Hive). Common issues arise when a person desires to take an SAT preparation course. These issues typically emerge when individuals realize the necessity of a SAT certificate to prepare for university admissions, whether domestically or internationally. Moreover, they may require a high score to apply for scholarships or simply to make their university application profile stand out. This recognition then leads them to begin questioning how this certificate can be achieved.

Students can be initiators when they recognize the necessity of the SAT certificate and begin seeking SAT preparation services, or when they have self-studied for the SAT but found it inefficient and need to find a place for guidance. Businesses can leverage these insights to design marketing strategies that highlight the importance and necessity of the SAT targeting these students (Indiafreenotes 2025). These strategies could be manifested through marketing materials such as social media posts or physical posters and standees placed in locations accessible to the target customers.

Parents can also be initiators. If parents are the ones initiating the discussion and identifying SAT preparation as the solution, they are likely those who understand their children's academic situation well. Businesses can utilize this information to create marketing strategies providing information about the necessity of the SAT specifically designed for parents. Beyond these two main groups, issues can also be raised through external influencers. These individuals can have a certain influence on parents or students, including peers and teachers. Additionally, media platforms serve as one of the catalysts initiating this process. As a result, an idea is introduced that creates a bridge to the purchasing process.

3.3.2 Influencer

Influencers are individuals who affect the product selection by providing information, comments, suggestions, and opinions about the product (College Hive). They are often trusted individuals or those with relevant expertise (Indiafreenotes 2025). According to IIMB Management Review (Verma et al. 2003, 3), the sources Influencers can rely on to provide suggestions include personal information, personal experience, public information, and commercial information.

Influencers can be students who independently research available SAT courses and form their assessments. Influencers may also include parents who usually play this role in

families by sharing their opinions and information about the brand, price, and quality (Indiafreenotes 2025). Additionally, this group can also be customers' friends, teachers, or educational counselors. Marketers can enhance positive influencer experiences through marketing strategies that highlight testimonials from former students, quality teaching staff, or effective learning methods.

3.3.3 Decider

Deciders are people who make the final decision on whether to purchase the product. Based on information gathered from previous stages and following an information filtering process, they evaluate options and make a decision. They are mostly the pillars of families or organizations (Indiafreenotes 2025).

In the SAT market context, they are parents who have a significant voice and hold financial authority in the family. The circumstances of each family define whether the Decider is the father or the mother. This group plays a crucial role in determining course sales outcomes. Therefore, marketers must understand this audience and develop effective marketing strategies to successfully persuade them.

As discussed in the previous section regarding the VALS model, parents who serve as purchase deciders are motivated by needs such as Achievement and Ideals. Additionally, other factors, such as value and reliability, also play important roles in influencing the decisions of Deciders.

These factors help customers minimize perceived risks, including functional risk, time risk, and financial risk. Specifically, functional risk occurs when a product received fails to meet customer expectations (Kotler & Keller 2012, 171). This means parents will select the option they perceive as offering the greatest value. Therefore, marketers must position their courses as providing superior value compared to competitors in the market. Functional risk directly impacts both the perceived value and reliability of the course.

Furthermore, two other risks that influence trust levels are financial risk and time risk. Financial risk occurs when the course does not justify the investment made. Meanwhile, time risk refers to the failure of the course, which leads to the buyer losing opportunity costs. This includes both the time invested in learning the unsuccessful course and the time spent finding another replacement course. (Kotler & Keller 2012, 171.)

High perceived risks can lead Deciders to modify, delay, or avoid purchasing decisions (Kotler & Keller 2012, 171). Therefore, marketers need to build strategies aimed at minimizing these risks. For instance, marketers can provide strong evidence, such as

performance data, output results, and detailed teaching methods, to facilitate Decider's evaluation process.

3.3.4 Buyer

The Buyer executes the transaction after making the decision. They determine the purchasing methods, such as location, time and purchase terms, and complete the transaction process. The Decider and Buyer are not necessarily the same person but can also be the same person (Indiafreenotes 2025). In the SAT context, parents typically serve as the Buyer, and these transactions can be carried out directly at SAT preparation centers or online.

Marketers should pay attention to factors affecting the purchasing process to create a clear procedure that facilitates seamless transaction execution. Given the high value of SAT courses, buyers may experience specific concerns both before and after payment. Therefore, marketers must prepare and provide comprehensive information about the course, commitment levels, next steps, and expected outcomes. This approach helps customers feel secure when making significant financial investments and understand what to expect following payment.

Additionally, whether the payment process is online or offline, it should be straightforward and simple to understand. In addition, marketers can also apply loyalty programs to encourage customers to return and purchase additional service packages in the future. This helps increase customer loyalty, thereby building strong relationships and creating opportunities for cross-selling products.

3.3.5 User

Users are individuals who directly use the product. The success of the product depends on the satisfaction of Users. (Indiafreenotes 2025.)

In the SAT market context, Users are the students. To achieve student satisfaction, SAT courses must meet their outcome expectations. These expectations typically include improving academic capabilities and achieving high SAT scores on the actual exam. Additionally, students also have expectations about service quality, including empathy and responsive support. For instance, teaching assistants providing regular support and being cared for throughout the course. Therefore, marketers must clearly understand these expectations to ensure course success. Providing users with excellent experiences will turn them into loyal customers, which drives sales performance and generates positive word-of-mouth effects about the course (Indiafreenotes 2025).

4 Sat Provider Analysis

4.1 Overview

The first SAT examination in Vietnam was conducted in 1999 by the Institute of International Education (IIE). In the past, students from Vietnam who wanted to take the SAT exam were required to go to Thailand (Nhan Dan 2006). Although the SAT was introduced in 1999, it only became widely used in recent years. In 2018, Vietnam National University Hanoi became the first university that accepted the SAT certificate for admissions. Following this, an increasing number of universities in the country began adopting the SAT into their admission standards, leading to a significant increase in the test's popularity. Between 2019 and 2023, the number of SAT test-takers increased from 1,781 to 3,500 (Tuoi Tre 2024b).

Although there are no official statistics on the number of centers or businesses providing SAT preparation services in Vietnam, the growth in test-takers indicates that demand for test preparation has risen since 2018-2019. According to supply-demand theory, increased demand leads to an increase in supply. This led to the development of a large number of SAT preparation centers and institutions at this time.

Chapter 4 examines SAT preparation providers in the Vietnamese market, focusing on well-known, highly rated, or prominent SAT providers. This analysis includes both centers that specialize in the SAT and businesses that offer the SAT as a supplementary service. These include study abroad centers that began expanding their services to include SAT preparation around 2018-2019, when demand for SAT instruction increased sharply. Standardized test preparation centers that offer multiple exams, including SAT, GMAT, TOEIC, IELTS, and GRE, are also analyzed. Additionally, individual tutors who focus only on SAT preparation, though not formal businesses, are included as well. This chapter aims to provide an overview of SAT providers in Vietnam and identify the factors influencing students' decisions in choosing a course.

4.2 Course & Service Offerings

This section explores existing SAT preparation courses and their structures. There are two main approaches to course organization. The first approach divides courses by SAT 2 sections: Math and Reading & Writing. Students can select the section in which they are weaker to improve their abilities. The second approach structures courses based on entry and target SAT scores, meaning both sections within a single course. Additionally, this

part provides information on the average course duration, class policies, and teaching formats of SAT preparation centers in Vietnam.

4.2.1 Course Levels

Target score-based courses

Most SAT courses in Vietnam are structured by target output scores. Typically a course divides into 4 to 5 classes with different levels. Each course alternates between Math and Reading and Writing instruction. After each course, learners typically improve by 100 to 200 points on average (DOL 2025a).

For example, Figure 8 describes the SAT program at American Study, a reputable and long-established English center in Vietnam. The SAT pathway at this center is divided into 4 main courses and 1 extra one-on-one course. The four main courses are divided by entry and exit score levels. The exit score of one course is the entry requirement for the next course.

This target score-based framework is also used by many other SAT providers in Vietnam, such as Phoenix Prep, QAS Academy, Stella Education, and Clever Academy. (Phoenix Prep 2025; QAS Academy a; Stella Education 2025; Clever Academy 2024.)

Figure 8: SAT course levels organized by target scores at American Study Education (adapted from American Study, 2025)

Section-based courses

As mentioned earlier, the SAT includes two sections: Math and Reading & Writing. Each section has similar scores, which range from 200 to 800 at maximum. While some centers organize courses by total target scores, others take a different approach. The course is designed with each part for each section, one for Math and one for Reading and Writing. Within each section, courses are divided into levels based on score ranges.

Figure 9 shows the course structure of Summit, one of the most well-known and long-established centers in Vietnam (Tripi 2025). The course is divided into two main sections: SAT Math and SAT Verbal, which includes reading and writing.

Figure 9: SAT course levels organized by section at Summit Education (Source: Summit)

Beyond Summit, other SAT preparation centers have a similar structure, including VietAccepted, ECE, and DOL English (VietAccepted 2025a; ECE 2024b; DOL 2025b). These centers all share a common pattern in that they have fewer math courses than verbal courses. This can be explained by the fact that most Vietnamese students perform better in the math section compared to reading and writing. Hieu D. Le, who graduated as valedictorian in economics and mathematics from UCLA, shared his perspective in an interview with Vietnamnet (2023). He pointed out that Vietnam's high school math curriculum is exceptionally strong, comparable to first-year university math at many major institutions worldwide. This shows that most Vietnamese students are provided with a solid foundation in mathematics during their high school. On the other hand, English is a second language in Vietnam, which leads to many students struggling with grammar, vocabulary, reading, and writing in English. As a result, many SAT course curricula are designed with extra time for the Reading and Writing section.

This section-based course structure allows students to focus on their weaker areas. Learners who struggle with mathematics focus on math courses, while those who struggle with reading and writing can take the verbal courses.

Course duration

Students need a basic level of English proficiency to take SAT courses. Most courses require a minimum entrance score of 800-1000 total points, approximately 5.0-5.5 on the IELTS (Ha Centre 2025).

Regardless of whether courses are structured by target scores or by section, the time required to complete the program from a basic level of 800 to 900 up to 1400 to 1500+ is typically 9 to 11 months.

4.2.2 Delivery Formats

SAT preparation centers in Vietnam can be divided into three groups based on their teaching format: offline only, both online and offline, and online only. Among SAT centers offering both formats, some, such as Stella Education and ECE, offer more offline than online courses. Most centers with offline formats are long-established institutions, for example, ECE founded in 2007 and Summit in 2010. In contrast, centers offering only online courses tend to be more recently established, such as DOL English, founded in 2018; VietAccepted, in 2014; and QAS Academy, in 2021 (DOL 2025c; VietAccepted 2025b; QAS Academy b).

This difference can be explained by two reasons. First, long-established centers have more stable finances to cover rental costs and staff, so they started with offline courses and later added online classes to adapt to market trends. Second, the development of technology and e-learning in Vietnam over the past decade has enabled newer centers to focus on online formats. In 2015, more than 100 educational institutions in Vietnam adopted online learning (OMT 2020). Moreover, online learning became more widespread during the COVID-19 pandemic (Vietnam Journal of Education 2024). As a result, newer centers prioritize online formats, which helps them save significant operating expenses.

4.2.3 Guarantee Policies

Some SAT preparation centers offer score guarantees under specific conditions. For instance, Stella Education and ECE require learners to complete a simulated SAT at the end of their course. If learners do not achieve the target score, the policy of the center depends on course compliance. Learners who have completed the required homework assignments and attended classes, typically at a rate of 90% to 100%, are entitled to retake the course free of charge. However, those who fail to meet these attendance and homework requirements are not eligible for a free retake, and the center assumes no responsibility for their results. Notably, neither center mentions any tuition refund policy in

cases where learners do not achieve the promised SAT score (Stella Education; ECE 2025).

4.3 Pricing Structures

The tuition fees for SAT courses in Vietnam vary significantly, ranging from 6 million to 25 million VND. Table 1 below shows the differences in tuition per hour and tuition per course among centers. The hourly rate is calculated by dividing the entire course fee by the total course hours. This information is included because the total course fee alone does not allow for a fair comparison between centers. For instance, in Table 1, the fee for a single course at Stella Education is 18 million VND, much higher than QAS Academy, which ranges from 8.57 to 9.6 million VND. However, when calculated per hour, the two centers have similar prices: 267,000 VND for QAS and 273,000 VND for Stella. This is because Stella offers 66 hours per course, nearly double the 36 hours offered by QAS. Therefore, including the cost per hour provides a more accurate basis for comparison.

Table 1: Tuition and Course Hours by Provider (Appendix 1)

SAT Provider	Course Division	Tuition/Hour (VND)	Tuition/Course (Million VND)	Hours/Course
Stella Education	By score band	~273,000	18	66
QAS Academy	By score band	~267,000	8.57-9.6	27-36
Phoenix Prep	By score band	~310,000-360,000	13.8-16.2	45
CLever Academy	By score band	~260,000-290,000	13-14.5	50
American Study	By score band	500,000	20	40
VietAccepted	By Section	~271,000-388,000	6.1-9.3	22.5-24

Summit	By Section	400,000-470,000	10.5 (Math); 20-25 (Verbal)	25 (Math); 50 (Verbal)
Dol English	By Section	300,000-360,000 (Super: 425,000)	9-13 (Super: 17)	30-42
ECE	By Section	250,000	6.5-12.5	20-50

As shown in figure 10, tuition fees can be divided into three segments. The high-price segment includes American Study and Summit, ranging from 400,000 to 500,000 VND per hour. The mid-price segment includes Phoenix Prep, VietAccepted, and DOL English, ranging from 300,000 to 360,000 VND per hour. DOL has a Super course that costs 425,000 VND per hour. However, it is still classified in the mid-price segment. This is because DOL offers six courses, five of which are priced between 300,000 and 350,000 VND per hour. The Super course is designed for students with an entering score of 1450 and an exit score of 1550, catering to a limited demographic due to its elevated difficulty level.

Consequently, the classification is predicated on the predominant courses that draw the most learners. Therefore, the classification is based on the majority of courses that attract more learners. The low-price segment includes ECE, QAS Academy, Stella Education, and CLever Academy, ranging from 250,000 to 290,000 VND per hour.

Figure 10: Hourly Tuition Comparison by Center (Appendix 1)

In addition to the price segments above, several centers offer one-on-one tutoring. These courses have no fixed duration or session limit, as instructors design personalized learning paths based on each student's ability. Therefore, one-on-one courses are priced on an hourly basis. For instance, Stella Education and QAS Academy charge between 1,200,000 and 1,300,000 VND per hour for private tutoring.

The high-price segment includes Summit and American Study, with course fees ranging from 20 to 25 million VND for a duration of approximately 2.5 to 4 months. These are long-established centers with over a decade of operation and a strong position in the Vietnamese education industry. In addition to SAT preparation, both centers are well known for their study abroad consulting services. Summit has consistently been known as a reliable option for parents and students for its educational excellence. Since 2015, Summit has been ranked among the top centers, with a significant number of students achieving high SAT scores (Summit 2015). However, many still consider Summit's tuition higher than the market average, while its class size is not significantly smaller than those in the mid-price segment. As a result, Summit's customers tend to be loyal families, where older siblings previously studied at the center, or those who purchase bundled SAT and study abroad packages.

On the other hand, American Study limits the class size to just 6 to 8 students. The center is well known for its study abroad programs, which helped thousands of Vietnamese students get accepted into top universities in the US. American Study justifies its high prices with experienced instructors, a strong reputation in study abroad consulting, and small class sizes. The center targets high-income families willing to invest in their children's education.

5 Discussion and Conclusion

The objective of this thesis is to provide readers with an understanding of the SAT preparation market in Vietnam by analyzing both the learner and provider sides. This is achieved by examining the characteristics, motivations, and behaviors of SAT learners, as well as the operational structures of existing SAT providers. This study aims to offer valuable reference information for organizations currently operating in SAT or businesses considering entering the market.

Learner Profile

From the SAT customer analysis, the typical profile of SAT learners in Vietnam consists of students with a certain level of English proficiency and from families with relatively good financial conditions. However, a student with poor academic ability but sufficient financial resources can still pursue the SAT with passion and a suitable study plan. In contrast, students having poor academic achievement and limited financial circumstances tend to be less likely to choose the SAT.

The main reason is that the SAT is not a general examination for all students but rather targets learners with specific goals. In 2023, approximately 546,000 students were admitted to universities (Tap chi dien tu Giao Duc Viet Nam 2024), while only about 3,500 students took the SAT in the same year (Tuoi Tre 2024b). This considerable difference indicates that the SAT primarily serves a small group of students with specific educational needs. This group is more concentrated in major cities, where socio-economic development is higher and study abroad opportunities are more common compared to rural areas or smaller provinces.

SAT Provider

The SAT provider market is categorized in three segments according to course pricing: premium, mid-range, and low-price. The premium group has courses with higher tuition fees and smaller class sizes. These courses are designed for customers with strong financial resources who are willing to pay extra for high-quality education. The mid-range group has the largest share, which serves the majority of SAT learners in Vietnam. The low-price segment consists of new market entrants or businesses that consider SAT courses as an additional service to attract customers to their primary products. The duration of the SAT course usually lasts from 2 to 4 months, with classes conducted 2-3 times per week. There are two common approaches to designing the course structure. First way is based on the overall target score, where courses are divided by entry and exit scores for the entire SAT. The other way is dividing Math and Verbal into two separate

courses, which allows students to focus on their weaker areas. These two models help students choose a learning path that suits their ability and personal goals. These two models help learners choose a learning path that suits their ability and personal goals.

Limitations

The VALS framework cited in Marketing Management was created and validated through surveys conducted in the United States. This model has not been adjusted or redeveloped for the Vietnamese consumer context. In America, people value an individualistic culture, while in Vietnam, people are strongly influenced by a collectivist culture. Most important decisions, such as choosing a course, are based on personal motivation and influenced by outside factors. This can be family, friends, and the surrounding community, such as social media. Moreover, Vietnamese values differ in many aspects, such as sacrifice, patience, frugality, and high academic pressure. These factors are not well represented in American consumer behavior models.

However, VALS is not entirely inaccurate. The model correctly describes basic human motivations through three main groups which are Achievement, Ideals, and Self-expression. Nevertheless, when applied to the Vietnamese market, VALS should be used with caution as a reference. It should be combined with practical research on customer needs and adapted to the local cultural context.

Future Research

The second limitation of this research is the lack of a large-scale quantitative survey targeting SAT learners. Such surveys could explore under what conditions students are willing to accept higher tuition fees. Beyond preparing for the SAT exam to achieve a good score, students also expect to feel satisfied with a course. This is a factor that many businesses rarely pay attention to.

The limitations of this research are due to time constraints and the difficulty of reaching a large number of SAT learners in Vietnam. Collecting a large survey sample of 200 to 300 people interested in the SAT is challenging within the scope of an undergraduate thesis. Therefore, a potential direction for future research is to conduct a large-scale quantitative survey to identify what factors influence learner expectations beyond preparing well for the SAT exam.

Conclusion

The SAT market in Vietnam will continue to grow, and more customers with different motivations and resources will emerge. Therefore, providers need to clearly identify their target customers to develop products strategically.

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Appendix 1. Summary of SAT courses across selected centers

No .	Center	Course Type	Courses Offered	Class Size	Mode	Tuition/ Hour (VND)	Tuition/ Course (million VND)	Entry - Target Score Range	Duration (months)	Total Hours
1	Stella Education	By score band	5	4-6	ON/OFF	273,000	18	0-1000; 1150; 1250; 1350; 1450+; 1500+	3	66
3	QAS Academy	By score band	3	8-25	ON	267,000	8.57-9.6	700-1100+; 1100-1300+; 1350-1450+	2.5-3	27-36
4	Phoenix Prep	By score band	4	15-18	ON/OFF	310,000-360,000	13.8-16.2	-	2.5	45
5	VietAccepted	By section	3	70-80	ON	271,000-388,000	6.1-9.3	-	2	22-24
6	Summit	By section	6	10-12	ON/OFF	400,000-470,000	10.5-23.5	450-500+; 550+; 600+; 640+; 680+; 650+	2.5	25-50
7	DOL English	By section	6	8-12	ON	300,000-360,000	9-12.5	V350-500+; V500-600+; V600-680+; M680-650+; M650-770+; 1450-1550+	2	30-42
8	ECE	By section	4	-	ON/OFF	250,000	6.5-12.5	0-400+; 280-580+; 580-680+; Math varies	2-3	20-50
9	Clever Academy	By score band	2	5-15	ON/OFF	260,000-290,000	13-14.5	5.5-1150+	3-4	50
10	American Study	By score band	3	6-8	ON/OFF	333,000-500,000	20-25	860-1150+; 1100-1250+; 1250-1400+	2.5-4	40-60
12	Etest	By score band	6	6-8	ON/OFF	-	-	Basic; 1000+; 1200+; 1300+; 1400+; 1500+	-	-